

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BASED ON
POLY(2-BROMO-PARA-XYLYLENE) AND CARBON FIBER
Hong Li, Aharon Moshonov and John D. Muzzy
School of Chemical Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, Georgia 30332-0100

ABSTRACT

A new thermoplastic composite towpreg based on poly(2-bromo-para-xylylene) (PBPX) and carbon fiber was produced through an in-situ electrochemical polymerization (ECP) of 2-bromo- α,α' -dibromo-para-xylylene (BDBPX). The polymerization was done in a three-compartment electrolysis cell. BDBPX was synthesized by the bromination of 2-bromo-para-xylylene. ECP has been shown to be an attractive combining process for the formation of carbon fiber towpreg. A composite of 40% polymer matrix by volume was achieved in 20 minutes by this process. The glass transition and melting temperatures for PBPX were found to be about 80° C and 270° C, respectively. Based on TGA scans under N₂, PBPX won't degrade until 430° C. A consolidated composite sample of PBPX and AS4 carbon fiber was made successfully through compression molding. Measurements of tensile and bending modulus were carried out using microtensile testing and dynamic mechanical testing respectively. Reasonable mechanical properties were found for this composite.

KEY WORDS: Electrochemical polymerization; Poly(2-bromo-para-xylylene); Carbon fiber; Towpreg; Thermoplastic composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

In earlier work by the authors [1], an aromatic thermoplastic and carbon fiber composite towpreg was produced through an in-situ electrochemical polymerization (ECP) of α,α' -dibromo-para-xylylene. Compared with other combining processes, the main advantages of this technique are simple operation, better bonding, individual fiber coating, ease of control, and high efficiency. A porous uniform poly-para-xylylene (PPX) coating with 40 percent weight gain was obtained in 10 to 15 minutes reaction.

It has been reported that PPX has unusually high thermal stability, attractive electrical

and is insoluble in all but a few solvents, which require about 300 °C before solution occurs [2, 3, 4]. It is a potential candidate for fiber-forming and polymer composite. However, thermal analysis of PPX shows that this polymer melts at about 430 °C, accompanied by considerable degradation [1], indicating a problem for melt processing. In our present work, an attempt at lowering the crystalline melting point of PPX by introducing a substituent on the phenyl ring was made. A modified xylene monomer, 2-bromo- α,α' -dibromo-para-xylene (BDBPX), was synthesized and then polymerized electrochemically on the carbon fiber surface. It is found that poly-2-bromo-para-xylylene (PBPX) melts at a much lower temperature (about 270 °C) than its degradation temperature (above 400 °C). A consolidated composite sample was made successfully from PBPX and AS4 carbon fiber tow prepreg by compression molding. The modulus of this unidirectional laminate is comparable to other AS4 composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials 2-bromo- α,α' -para-xylene was prepared by bromination of 2-bromo-para-xylene (BPX) (F.W. 185.07; M.P. 9 - 10 °C; B.P. 199 -210 °C), which was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company and was used in as-received condition. The brominating agent, N-bromo-succinimide (NBS) (F.W. 177.99; M.P. 180-183 °C) was also purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company and used after purification. Carbon tetrachloride, obtained from Fisher Chemical Company, was used as the solvent for the bromination reaction after distillation.

In the electrochemical polymerization process, unsized Hercules AS-4 3K carbon fiber tow was used as the working electrode without any pretreatment. N,N-dimethyl-formamide (DMF), purchased from Aldrich, was used as the solvent. The supporting electrolyte was reagent grade Tetra-ethyl-ammonium-bromide (TEAB) obtained from Alfa Chemical Company.

2.2 Apparatus Chemical synthesis of 2-bromo- α,α' -para-xylene was carried out in a flask equipped with a reflux column. A Phillips 150 W light with clear (non frosted) glass was fixed close to the flask to supply light irradiation for the reaction. The outlet of the reflux column was surrounded by an argon atmosphere.

Electrochemical polymerizations were carried out in a glass cell with three compartments, as described previously [1].

2.3 Procedure

2.3.1 Purification of N-bromo-succinimide N-bromo-succinimide (NBS) (30 g) was dissolved in 300 ml of boiling water and filtered through a fluted filter into a flask immersed in an ice bath. The filtered solution was let stand in the ice bath for two hours, leading to the formation of purified N-bromo-succinimide crystals. The crystals were then filtered, washed thoroughly with about 100 ml of ice-cold water and drained on a Buchner

2.3.1 **Bromination of 2-bromo-para-xylene (BPX)** 2-bromo-para-xylene (BPX) (4.94 g, 26.7 mmol), NBS (10.6 g, 59.5 mmol) and carbon tetrachloride (CTC) (100 ml, freshly distilled) were combined in a dry flask. NBS does not dissolve in CTC and participated at the bottom of the flask. The mixture was irradiated with a Phillips 150 W light and heated to 78 °C for one hour under continuous stirring. By this time, all of the solid floated. The mixture was allowed to cool down. A clear solution was collected after the solid was removed by filtration. The filtered solid was washed with carbon tetrachloride and the washed out solution was combined with collected solution. CTC solvent was removed by vacuum evaporation to leave approximately 3 g of a slightly yellow gummy solid. This solid was further crystallized by dissolving them in boiled hexane, then cooled down to room temperature. The crystals precipitated and were separated from the solution by filtration. The resulting products were finally vacuum evaporated, leaving about 2 g of white crystals of 2-bromo- α,α' -para-xylene.

2.2 **Electrochemical polymerization** The procedures for electrochemical polymerization of xylene derivatives have been reported previously [1]. BDBPX was polymerized on the carbon fiber surfaces in a three-compartment electrolysis cell at various potentials and reaction times.

2.3 **Consolidation of towpreg** Unidirectional composite laminates of PBPX and AS-4 carbon fiber were made through consolidating towpreg by compression molding. The desired number of layers of towpreg were put in parallel in the cavity of a matched-die steel mold with dimensions of 20 x 100 x 0.25 mm. The mold was then heated rapidly on the hot platen of the press to 270 °C. A pressure of around 3 MPa was applied and held for one minute. A Wabash press with 50 ton capacity was used. A lower pressure could not be achieved on this machine because of the high capacity of the press. The mold was then cooled down at a rate of about 5 °C per minute to room temperature before demolding.

2.4 **Characterization of towpreg and consolidated tape** Towpregs obtained by ECP were characterized by different techniques. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) (Perkin Elmer, Series 7 Thermal Analysis System) was used for thermal stability testing at a heating rate of 20 °C per minute. A Leitz microscope (Laborlux 12 Pol) equipped with a hot stage was employed to inspect polymer melting while being heated at 10 °C per minute. Topology of the towpreg was examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The specimen was sputtered with a thin layer of gold and observed with a Cambridge Stereoscan 90 SEM operating at 15 kV. A Wide Angle X-ray Diffraction (WAXD) study was carried out by means of Rigaku Rotaflex Ru-200 Rotating Anode X-ray generator. WAXD photographs were taken with a flat film camera. The operating voltage was 4.5 kV with a current of 100 mA. Ni filtered Cu-K α radiation was used and the pinhole size was 0.02 mm. The distance between the sample and the film was 55 mm. The transition temperature was tested by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) (Perkin Elmer DSC instrument) at a heating rate of 20 °C per minute.

Consolidated composite samples were viewed by Zeiss ICM 405 inverted stage microscope. Specimens were prepared by embedding composite sample in an epoxy mounting material (Epon 627 by Shell Co.), which was then cured overnight at room temperature. The cross section of the imbedded composite was polished on 150, 400 and 600 grit emery paper respectively with running water and finally polished with alumina powder to 0.05 mm.

The tensile modulus of PBPX / AS-4 carbon fiber composite was measured by a micromechanical tensile tester, built by Micromechanics Lab of the Georgia Tech Research Institute. The displacement was monitored by a Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT). The unidirectional composite sample with a gauge length of 28 mm was mounted on the machine by two aluminum clamping grips and was tested at a deformation rate of 0.01 mm per second under room temperature. The sample load-displacement was recorded by X-Y plotter.

The flexural modulus of PBPX / AS4 carbon fiber composite was estimated using a Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analyzer (DMTA) (Polymer Labs). Unidirectional composite laminate samples with the dimensions of approximately 5 mm by width and 0.2 mm by thickness were tested. The span was 50 mm.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis of BDBPX The synthesis of BDBPX was done by a single step bromination of 2-bromo-para-xylene. The scheme of this reaction is shown as follows:

In the first few runs of this reaction, 5 per mole cent of Dibenzoyl peroxide in BPX was added in order to initiate the reaction. But this was shown to be unnecessary in later experiments. With the irradiation of a clear Phillips 150 W light and heating to 78° C , bromination was carried out very rapidly and effectively without initiator.

Different ratios of BPX to NBS were tested and a molar ratio of 1:2.3 gave a short reaction time and high product purity. Over brominized products were detected by NMR spectroscopy when an excess amount of NBS was used. Under the reaction conditions described above, a yield of about 30% was obtained. The H-NMR spectrum of the final product is shown in Figure 1. Two equivalent height peaks between 4 and 5 ppm correspond to two protons on the methylene bromide group respectively. Those peaks appearing between 7 ppm and 8 ppm are attributed to

the phenyl protons. Based on the H-NMR spectrum combined with a material balance analysis, no overbrominated nor unbrominated BPX was present in the final product. A very pure 2-bromo- α,α' -dibromo-para-xylene was obtained after recrystallization. No effort to increase the yield was made.

3.2 Formation of PBPX and AS4 carbon fiber towpreg The mechanism of electrochemical polymerization for PPX on carbon fibers, presented previously [1], should also apply to the formation of PBPX. Figure 2 shows the initial current that passes through the solution versus polarization potential. The first rise in current, starting at about -0.9 volt, is the initiation of polymerization and corresponds to the electron transfer from the carbon fiber electrode to the monomer. The second rise in current, starting near -2.0 volts, is associated with side reactions, such as the cathodic reduction of DMF solvent [5].

Weight gains of fibers after ECP were measured and the corresponding efficiencies of polymer coating were calculated. The polymer coating efficiency is defined as the percentage of the total quantity of electricity passing through the cell used to produce the polymer on the fiber surface. In Figure 3 the efficiencies for the formation of PPX and PBPX are compared. It shows that after bromine substitution on the phenyl ring of DBPX, the ECP efficiency drops down to 80% at the maximum point. This behavior may be attributed to a side reaction related to the bromine group on the phenyl ring. However, the weight gain of the fibers by ECP still can reach as high as 50% for 20 minutes reaction at -1.4 volts, as shown in Figure 4.

3.3 Thermal stability The thermal stability of PBPX produced by ECP was tested on towpreg samples by TGA. Figure 5 shows that PBPX is thermally stable. No obvious degradation occurred before 450° C under N₂. Compared with PPX, there is no significant difference in thermal stability between PBPX and PPX.

3.4 Topology The topology of PBPX towpreg was examined by SEM. Figure 6 shows a porous polymer coating, which is due to the mechanism of this electrochemical polymerization process [1]. SEM pictures were also taken on PBPX towpreg after heat treatment. Samples were heated to 350° C at a rate of 20° C per minute, then cooled down to room temperature at the same rate. As shown in Figure 7, the porous coating of PBPX has collapsed or flowed, leading to a smoother coating. This behavior is different from PPX towpreg, which did not show any obvious polymer melting after heating to 350° C.

3.5 Polymer melting Polymer melting was monitored through a light microscope equipped with a hot stage. Towpreg samples were heated at a rate of about 10° C per minute. The porous PBPX coating melted around 260° C and then covered the fibers to form a continuous coating. This behavior was not observed in the PPX towpreg.

3.6 T_m and T_g The DSC traces of a PBPX towpreg sample are shown in Figure 8. Both

curve occurred at about 270 °C. Compared with the hot stage light microscopy observations, it can be confirmed as crystal melting. During cooling, an endotherm peak appeared at around 200 °C, indicating recrystallization of the polymer. However, the new crystals melt at 245 °C, lower than that of original crystals. In the WAXD experiment, no obvious change in crystal dimensions before and after melting was observed. Therefore, this change in T_m may be due to less order in the new crystals formed during a rather fast cooling. The difference in melting temperature between PPX and PBPX is almost 160 °C. Substitution of bromine on the phenyl ring lowers the symmetry of the polymer chains, which affected the packing and crystallization of the polymer.

The glass transition temperature of PBPX was not apparent in a DSC trace. A DMTA experiment was carried out to observe the glass transition point. Consolidated PBPX and AS4 carbon fiber composite sample was tested under bending at a frequency of 10 cycles per second. The plot of dissipation factor, $\tan \delta$, versus temperature shows a glass transition at about 85 °C (Figure 9).

It was reported that poly(2-chloro-para-xylylene), made by vacuum vapor-phase pyrolysis and followed by polymerization on condensation, has a glass transition at 85 °C and a T_m at 270 °C [6]. These transitions are consistent with the transitions obtained for PBPX in this work.

3.7 Crystallization WAXD studies were carried out on PBPX towpregs as polymerized and after heating. The heating was performed by putting the sample in an oven at 300 °C for 20 minutes and then slowly cooling down the oven to room temperature in two hours. Shown in Figure 10 is an X-ray diffraction pattern for towpreg as polymerized. Two outer spots on the picture were due to the graphite crystals of carbon fiber oriented in the fiber axis. The ring is attributed to the random oriented polymer crystals. It is clear that PBPX crystallized on the fiber surface during ECP process. No change in the WAXD pattern was observed after the towpreg was heat treated. In contrast, the WAXD pattern for PPX changed after heat treatment.

3.8 Consolidation of towpreg The compression molding for towpreg consolidation was done at 270 °C. Figure 11 is a microscopic photograph on the cross-section of the consolidated composite sample. It seems that resin melted very well and separated fibers individually. No debonding between fiber and matrix and no voids were observed.

3.9 Mechanical properties of the consolidated composite Dynamic flexural modulus of PBPX and AS4 carbon fiber composite was estimated by DMTA. This instrument is designed for measuring dynamic modulus of polymers. However, it requires small samples and can clearly tell the difference of flexural modulus between two different composites, as is desired in this investigation. The sample undergoing analysis is subjected to a sinusoidal force of known magnitude, applied to its mid point via the central drive shaft of the mechanical spectrometer.

operate the system and to calculate the numerical values for $\text{Log } E'$. The analysis was performed at a frequency of 10 Hz. The testing was conducted in a temperature range of 50°C to 250°C . From the result shown in Figure 12, the dynamic flexural modulus of PBPX / AS4 increases slowly from room temperature to the glass transition temperature of PBPX (about 80°C) and then decreases. For the purpose of comparison, a commercial APC-2 unidirectional composite, made of PEEK and AS4 carbon fiber by ICI, was also tested under same conditions. A dynamic flexural initial modulus of 64.6 GPa was obtained at 50°C , which is much lower than manufacturer's data of 121 GPa, tested by different methods and conditions [7]. A calibration was made based on the commercial data of APC-2 and a flexural modulus of 89.5 GPa at 50°C was obtained for PBPX composite. When the sample was heated at 3°C per minute to 200°C , a dynamic flexural modulus of about 72 GPa still remained, almost 80% of its modulus at 50°C .

The tensile modulus of PBPX composite was also evaluated by a microtensile tester. Unidirectional composite samples, with an average gauge length of 28 mm, were tested at a deformation rate of 0.01 mm per second under room temperature. Result shows an initial tensile modulus of about 90 GPa.

The test results suggest that PBPX / AS4 carbon fiber composite has reasonable mechanical properties. Therefore, this towpreg, as well as the ECP process, has a good potential in the application of advanced thermoplastic composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. A pure 2-bromo- α,α' -dibromo-para-xylyene was synthesized through bromination of α,α' -dibromo-para-xylyene.
2. A towpreg of PBPX/AS4 was obtained through an electrochemical polymerization process.
3. The efficiency of polymer coating for 2-bromo- α,α' -dibromo-para-xylyene is lower than that of α,α' -dibromo-para-xylyene. But a 50% weight gain of fiber can still be achieved in 20 minutes.
4. Both PBPX and PPX exhibit a degradation temperature of around 450°C under nitrogen atmosphere.
5. PBPX shows a T_g at approximately 80°C and melts at approximately 270°C .
6. A unidirectional PBPX and AS4 consolidated composite tape was made through thermal compression of PBPX/AS4 towpreg.

7. PBPX/AS4 unidirectional composite tape has an initial tensile modulus of 90 GPa and an initial flexural modulus of 89.5 GPa at 50° C.

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6. REFERENCE

1. H. Li, A. Moshonov, and J. D. Muzzy, Polymer Composites, in press, (1991).
2. L.A. Errede, and R.S. Gregorian, Journal of Polymer Science, **60**, 21 (1962).
3. L.A. Errede, and M. Szwarc, Quarter Review, **12**, 301 (1958).
4. W.D. Niegisch, Polymer Letters, **4**, 531 (1966).
5. R.E. Visco, Proceedings of Electrochemical Society Meeting, Spring, 1967, 67 (1967).
6. Gorham, W.F. Journal of Polymer Science, Part A-1, **4**, 3027 (1966).
7. ICI Fiberite Data Sheet, 3a, Fiberite Corporation, 1986

Figure 1 H-NMR spectrum of 2-bromo- α, α' -dibromo-p-xylene

Figure 2 Initial current vs polarization potential

Figure 3 Comparison of current efficiency for the formation of poly(p-xylylene) and poly(2-bromo-p-xylylene)

Figure 4 Weight gain of fibers vs polarization potential

Figure 5 Thermogravimetric analysis scan of PBPX and carbon fiber towpreg

Figure 6 SEM photograph of PBPX and carbon fiber towpreg as polymerized by ECP

Figure 7 SEM photograph of PBPX and carbon fiber towpreg after heat treatment

Figure 8 DSC trace of PBPX and carbon fiber towpreg as polymerized by ECP

Figure 9 DMTA scan of consolidated PBPX and carbon fiber composite showing Tg of polymer matrix

Figure 10 X-ray diffraction pattern of PBPX and carbon fiber towpreg

Figure 11 Microscopic photograph of consolidated PBPX and carbon fiber composite

Figure 12 DMTA scan of consolidated PBPX and carbon fiber composite